

Inter-Comparison Potentials of Ag/AgCl Electrodes in Aqueous Solution

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The inter-comparison potentials of Ag/AgCl electrodes in aqueous HCl solutions of different concentrations prepared by a number of different methods, have been measured at room temperature. It has been found that among different electrodes prepared by the same method, the inter-comparison potentials are quite low (0.05 mV for thermo-electrolytic, 0.2 mV for electrolytic electrodes); though that between the electrodes prepared differently is rather high. The E° value of one thermo-electrolytic electrode obtained from E.M.F. measurements in the cell: $H_2/HCl(m) AgCl/Ag$, and suitable extrapolation, has been found to be +0.2225V at 26.5°C.

Silver-silver halide electrodes constitute one of the most important types of reversible electrodes of the second kind, which owe their usefulness mainly to (i) their comparatively easy preparation; (ii) their inertness, and consequent non-contamination of the experimental medium; (iii) their suitability, particularly for setting up cells without liquid junctions; and finally (iv) their stability and high degree of reproducibility. However, for purposes of precise E.M.F. measurements, it is necessary to characterise the electrodes prepared by a number of different methods, so that the possible effects of impurities and contaminations introduced inadvertently during preparation, of surface films, or of variations in crystal structure etc. may be assessed before-hand and the most suitable electrode identified. Measurement of inter-comparison potentials of different electrodes (in a number of different solutions preferably), or else their bias potentials against a suitable aged reference electrode (if available), constitutes a convenient method of characterisation of electrodes. In our investigation of standard potentials of Ag-AgCl electrodes in different non-aqueous media, the electrodes prepared by a number of different methods described below have been characterised, in absence of a suitable aged reference, by measurement of inter-comparison potentials in aqueous solutions.

The potentials were measured in a 'pear' shaped, multinecked electrode vessel (75 c.c.) described elsewhere¹, accommodating simultaneously four study electrodes and a hydrogen electrode system, all dipping into 10 ml. of test solution. The electrode tubes (carrying B 5 cones on the upper side to fit into the vessel) were about 3 mm in diameter and 12 cm in length, carrying at the bottom platinum pieces of the electrodes spot-welded to about 6 cm of fine (diameter 0.2 mm) platinum wire running through a minimum of about 4 cm long glass seal formed from the well molten pyrex. This ensures leak-proof pyrex. The potentials were measured with an L. N. Type K2 potentiometer and a moving coil galvanometer of sensitivity 1 mm/meter at 10^{-5} V.

The *electrolytic electrodes*² were of two different types in construction: (i) the Gordon disc electrode, and (ii) the 'wire' electrode, where the electrode pieces consist respectively

1. M. Sengupta, G. C. Pal and D. N. Biswas, *Science and Culture* (Calcutta). 1967, **33**, 337.

2. Reference Electrodes, ed. D. J. G. Ives and J. C. Janz. Academic Press Inc., New York, 1961, p. 179.

of a small platinum disc (diameter 3 mm, thickness 0.3 mm) sealed flush to the glass, and a stout platinum wire (length 1 cm, diameter 1 mm). The electrode pieces were very thoroughly cleaned and then silver plated in an 'H' shaped cell with separate anode and cathode compartments in 1% potassium argento-cyanide solution to which a few drops of dilute silver nitrate was added to remove free cyanide, for about 6 hrs at about 0.15 mA. (The potassium argento-cyanide was prepared by first precipitating silver cyanide from (A.R., B.D.H.) silver nitrate and potassium cyanide and after thorough washing, dissolving it (2 gms) in hot potassium cyanide (1 gm) solution. The potassium argento-cyanide obtained on cooling was washed and recrystallised repeatedly (4-5 times) from hot water.) The silver plated electrodes were washed in 1:1 ammonium hydroxide solution for about 4 hrs. and then in running conductivity water for two days, and then chloridised in dark in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid solution at 0.75 mA for 10 minutes. The pinkish-brown electrodes were washed very thoroughly, and aged in the dark in dilute hydrochloric acid solution.

In the *thermo-electrolytic electrodes*², the electrode piece was a small (5-6 mm long) spiral of 2-3 turns of 0.5 mm diameter platinum wire. This was thoroughly cleaned and then covered with a thick paste of silver oxide* in conductivity water. After superficial drying of the paste, the electrodes were heated gradually in a furnace at a temperature of about 450°C for half an hr, whereby silver oxide was reduced to a fine coat of metallic silver on the platinum wire. The electrodes were then chloridised in N hydrochloric acid solution at 0.75 mA for 10 minutes. The hydrochloric acid solution was obtained by proper dilution of constant-boiling hydrochloric acid*. It was found that after a number of chloridisations from the same hydrochloric acid solution, the silver chloride formed on the electrode (in dark) was pink. The electrodes were thoroughly washed with conductivity water.

The *thermal electrodes*² were prepared by decomposing at 650°C for 5 minutes, on small-spiral platinum electrode pieces as above, a paste of 1.362 gms of silver oxide with 0.151 gms silver chlorate*. The electrodes obtained were consistently white.

The intercomparison potentials of the above electrodes, as also the E.M.F.'s of the cells: $H_2/HCl(m) AgCl(s)/Ag$ using the above Ag/AgCl electrodes one after another in a number of increasingly dilute HCl solutions, were then measured. The intercomparison potentials of the 'disc' and Nos. 5 and 6 thermo-electrolytic electrodes (cf figure) against the 'wire' electrode (negative) were 0.53, 2.44 and 2.35 mV respectively soon after preparation, and changed gradually to -0.05, 1.5 and 1.3 mV after ageing for 3 weeks. It will be seen that the intercomparison potentials of the two electrolytic electrodes (0.05 mV) and the two thermo-electrolytic electrodes (0.2 mV) among themselves were tolerably low, though those between any two electrodes prepared in different manners were rather high. The intercomparison potential of the thermal electrodes with respect to any one of the above was, however, very high (~ 10 mV), so that these electrodes were not considered suitable for further work.

The measured E.M.F. values (E) of the $H_2/HCl(m) AgCl(s)/Ag$ cells using the different Ag/AgCl electrodes in HCl solutions of different dilutions at 26.5°C were used to calculate the quantity $E' = (E + 0.1188 \log m - 0.0600\sqrt{m})$ for each electrode at the different concentrations, which is shown graphically in the figure. This should give a

*The silver oxide prepared as prescribed² was washed 25-30 times to free it completely from soluble impurities. The silver chlorate prepared/as prescribed² was recrystallised 5-6 times from hot water. The constant-boiling hydrochloric acid was prepared by twice distilling the A.R., B.D.H. product,

linear plot at sufficiently low concentration regions, the E° value of the cell being obtained from the intercept³. It is seen that the No. 5 thermo-electrolytic electrode leads to an E° value of +0.2225 volts, in close agreement with the known standard potential of Ag/AgCl electrode at 25°C. It is seen also that No. 6 thermo-electrolytic electrode would lead to a closely similar E° value, while the electrolytic electrodes would lead to E° values less by about 1.2 mV.

FIG. 1

This result shows that the thermo-electrolytic electrodes prepared as described above are the most suitable ones, the electrolytic electrodes being also not entirely unsuitable. It may be remarked, however, that the contention² that the electrode (here electrolytic) with the most negative inter-comparison potential (or bias potential) value should be considered to be the most suitable one, because of its minimum free energy content, is not entirely borne out from the above results.

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